

Heat Transfer Analysis of Full-Load Ground Testing of the Historical Aggregate A4

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Abstract

This paper describes the results of a comprehensive reverse engineering analysis of the setup used for full-load ground testing of the historical Aggregate 4 (A4) rocket from a thermodynamical point of view.

Starting out from data given in the literature such as thrust, mass flow of oxygen and alcohol, numerical values of nozzle exit velocity, the temperature and molar mass of the exhaust gas mixture (consisting of CO₂ and water vapor) are calculated. The isentropic expansion in the Laval nozzle allows the combustion chamber temperature to be derived. Stagnation pressure and temperature at the crest of the flame deflector are used as starting point to calculate the heat transfer to the hundreds of cooling pipes mounted on the deflector surface. This deflector system is treated as a heat exchanger between the hot gas exhaust of the rocket motor and the cooling water flowing through the pipes. From this the overall heat transfer capacity is established and yields an interesting result: Additional external water must be injected to cool down the exhaust gases to prevent structural damage to the flame deflector. This spray water allows a reduction of the mass flow of cooling water in the deflector pipes. Based on these results the pressure losses in the manifold can be calculated by using resistance coefficients and friction factors from the literature. These pressure and power losses are added up to determine the ratings of the three pumps delivering cooling water to the historical test stand.

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Figure 1: Sketch of the overall setup (not to scale)

1. Introduction

The *Aggregate 4* was at its time the “most highly developed piece of equipment in the world”,¹ and was developed through twelve years of research, design, testing, and production. After each major development step the aggregate (i. e. the overall rocket) was mounted vertically in a tower like structure for testing. This test stand enabled the calculated values for various pressures, temperatures, gas velocities, thrust, the performance of the turbo pump assembly, the operation of the fuel spray nozzles, the control systems to be verified and for the overall behavior of the rocket to be tested, as shown in figure 1.

Carrying out these tests under full load conditions was a sine qua non. Therefore, the tower was placed above a structure 90 m in length and 15 m wide that had to absorb and transfer the enormous heat of 500 MW at the exhaust nozzle which results in more than 8 MWh during a 60 second test run. This structure was designed as a double sided flame deflector, studded on its surface with more than 400 steel tubes through which cooling water circulated.

In this paper an attempt is made to recreate the aero-thermodynamic design calculation in order to shed some light on the critical part of rocket testing in the early days of rocketry. How did they manage transferring the enormous heat from the rocket motor to the cooled flame deflector during full-load tests in the early 1940s? How were (and are) such test facilities designed from first principles?

This reverse engineering attempt is justified since no actual documents containing such calculations for the test stand P-VII in Peenemünde are known to exist nowadays. Neither the Bundesarchiv in Berlin and Freiburg nor the Deutsches Museum in Munich nor the HTM in Peenemünde have any documents detailing this crucial aspect. Even the AGARD symposium “History of Guided Missiles Development” of 1956 chaired by Theodore von Kármán ne-

¹Cf. Freund (2020).

Parameter	Value	Comment
Thrust	$F = 250$ kN	cf. (A4, 1945, p.)
Exhaust mass flow	$\dot{m} = 130$ kg/s	cf. (A4, 1945, p.)
A-Stoff (liquid oxygen)	72 kg/s	cf. (A4, 1945, p.)
B-Stoff (alcohol and water)	58 kg/s	cf. (Przybilski, 2002, p.) 45% ethanol $\hat{=}$ 26.1 kg/s 30% methanol $\hat{=}$ 17.4 kg/s 25% H ₂ O $\hat{=}$ 14.5 kg/s
Nozzle exit diameter	$d_2 = 710$ mm	Values vary around this
Nozzle exit area	$A_2 = 0.396$ m ²	
Combustion chamber pressure	$p_1 = 1520$ kPa	cf. (A4, 1945, p.)
External pressure	$p_2 = 100$ kPa	atmospheric pressure

Table 1: Known data used as basis for the following derivations

Substance	Molar mass M in kg/kmol	Mass flow \dot{m} in kg/s	Molar flow \dot{n} in kmol/s
Oxygen (O ₂)	$16 + 16 = 32$	72	2.25
Ethanol (C ₂ H ₅ OH)	$24 + 5 + 16 + 1 = 46$	26.1	0.57
Methanol (CH ₃ OH)	$12 + 3 + 16 + 1 = 32$	17.4	0.54
Water (H ₂ O)	$2 + 16 = 18$	14.5	0.81
Exhaust sum	31.2	130	4.17

Table 2: \dot{m} and \dot{n} for the various components

glects this interesting engineering aspect. The contemporary technical literature does not contain any information about this topic, too.

2. What is known?

The following calculations are based on the known values listed in table 1.² Thrust is described by $F = \dot{m}v_2$ with v_2 denoting the exhaust gas velocity:³

$$v_2 = \frac{F}{\dot{m}} = 1923 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$$

Mass flow is the product of the molar mass times molar flow, $\dot{m} = M\dot{n}$ so that $\dot{n} = \frac{\dot{m}}{M}$. Table 2 shows the mass and molar flows of the various constituents.

The two main combustion reactions are described as follows:

²The area designations are based on a Laval nozzle.

³ v_1 is typically set to 0 in such calculations. To simplify notation, we use the equal sign not only for mathematical equalities but also for calculated values which are only approximates.

Figure 2: Combustion chamber and nozzle

Figure 3: Isobaric heat capacity of the exhaust gas

The equation of continuity for the nozzle exhaust is⁴

$$\dot{m} = A_2 v_2 \rho_2 = \frac{A_2 v_2 p_2}{RT_2}.$$

The exhaust temperature follows from the equation above and is

$$T_2 = \frac{A_2 v_2 p_2}{R \dot{m}} = 2194 \text{ K}.$$

Using the molar masses of water $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 18.02 \text{ kg/kmol}$ and carbon dioxide $M_{\text{CO}_2} = 44.01 \text{ kg/kmol}$ we can now determine the volume fractions of these two gases as follows:

$$M = \sum_{i=1}^2 r_i M_i = r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} + r_{\text{CO}_2} M_{\text{CO}_2}$$

$$r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \frac{M - M_{\text{CO}_2}}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - M_{\text{CO}_2}} = 0.493$$

$$r_{\text{CO}_2} = 1 - r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.507$$

Figure 2 shows a schematic of the combustion chamber with its Laval nozzle and the relevant parameters. The isobaric molar heat capacity depends on temperature according to the approximation

$$C_p = a + b \frac{T}{1000} + c \frac{T^2}{1000^2} + d \frac{T^3}{1000^3} = M c_p \text{ kJ/kmol K}$$

with $a = 21.57$, $b = 63.74$, $c = -40.53$, $d = 9.684$ for CO_2 and $a = 30.38$, $b = 9.621$, $c = 1.185$, $d = 0$ for H_2O .⁵ This allows to calculate the heat capacities of CO_2 and H_2O in a temperature range of 273 K to about 1300 K. Since no better formulas were available, the above formula was used for temperatures

⁴The gas constant $R = \frac{R^*}{M} \approx 8,3145/31.2 \approx 0.267 \text{ kJ/kg K}$ with R^* denoting the universal gas constant.

⁵Cf. https://de.wikibooks.org/wiki/Tabellensammlung_Chemie/_spezifische_W%C3%A4rmekapazit%C3%A4ten, 27.04.2021

up to 2500 K in the following so that the results will be approximations only. Figure 3 shows the isobaric heat capacity of the exhaust gas, which is the basis for all of the following calculations.

In the next step, the overall exhaust volume flow and the partial volume flows as well as the mass and molar flows will be calculated.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{V} &= \frac{\dot{m}RT}{p} = 762 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}} && \text{exhaust volume flow} \\
 \dot{V}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} &= r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}\dot{V} = 376 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}} && \text{exhaust volume flow H}_2\text{O} \\
 \dot{V}_{\text{CO}_2} &= r_{\text{CO}_2}\dot{V} = 386 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{s}} && \text{exhaust volume flow CO}_2 \\
 \dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} &= \dot{V}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}p \frac{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{R^*T} = 37.1 \text{ kg/s} && \text{mass flow H}_2\text{O} \\
 \dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} &= \dot{V}_{\text{CO}_2}p \frac{M_{\text{CO}_2}}{R^*T} = 93.1 \text{ kg/s} && \text{mass flow CO}_2 \\
 \dot{n}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} &= \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} = 2.06 \text{ kmol/s} && \text{molar flow H}_2\text{O} \\
 \dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2} &= \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2}}{M_{\text{CO}_2}} = 2.11 \text{ kmol/s} && \text{molar flow CO}_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Using these values the exhaust gas velocity can be determined as

$$v_2 = \frac{\dot{V}}{A} = 1924 \text{ m/s}$$

which is close to v_2 as determined above. The molar flow itself is not changed due to the combustion and is 4.17 kmol/s.

3. The thermodynamics of the gas flow

The enthalpy/entropy diagram, figure 4, shows the change of state in the Laval nozzle of the rocket engine. The inlet temperature results from the first law of thermodynamics. The isobaric heat capacity c_p depends on the temperature. Therefore the entry temperature will be guessed and c_p corrected iteratively.

The 1st law of thermodynamics yields

$$P + \dot{Q} = \dot{m} \left(h_2 - h_1 + \frac{v_2^2 - v_1^2}{2} + g(z_2 - z_1) \right).$$

Since there is no work or heat input in the Laval nozzle, we have $P = \dot{Q} = 0$ and $v_1 = 0$, $z_2 - z_1 = 0$. Thus the enthalpy difference is

$$h_1 - h_2 = c_{p12}(T_1 - T_2) = \frac{v_2^2}{2} \text{ and}$$

Figure 4: Enthalpy/entropy diagram

$$T_1 = T_2 + \frac{v_2^2}{2c_{p12}} = 2984 \text{ K.}$$

The mean temperature between nozzle inlet and outlet is thus

$$T_m = \frac{T_1 + T_2}{2} = 2589 \text{ K.}$$

The average isobaric molar heat capacity of the water vapor is $Mc_{pm\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 63.2 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$ and that of carbon dioxide is $Mc_{pm\text{CO}_2} = 83 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$. From these values the isobaric molar heat capacity of the exhaust gas mixture can be determined:

$$Mc_{pm} = r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}Mc_{pm\text{H}_2\text{O}} + r_{\text{CO}_2}Mc_{pm\text{CO}_2} = 73.2 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$$

From this follows the isobaric heat capacity

$$c_{p12} = \frac{Mc_{pm}}{M} = 2.34 \text{ kJ/kg K.}$$

We now need to determine the isentropic exponent

$$\kappa_m = \frac{Mc_{pm}}{Mc_{pm} - R^*} = 1.13.$$

The inlet temperature is in good accordance with Statistics (2021):

$$T_1 = 2194 + \frac{1923^2}{2 \cdot 2.34 \cdot 1000} = 2984 \text{ K}$$

Using these values the exhaust velocity can also be calculated according to Saint-Venant-Wantzel:

$$v_2 = \sqrt{\frac{2k_m}{k_m - 1} RT_1 \left(1 - \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1} \right)^{\frac{k_m - 1}{k_m}} \right)} = 1929 \text{ m/s}$$

This velocity v_2 is in good accordance with the value of 1923 m/s found in the literature thus confirming the inlet temperature.

The stagnation temperature on the crest and surface of the flame deflector can be computed using the Bernoulli equation

$$p_2 + \frac{\rho_2}{2} v_2^2 = p_{\text{stag}} + \frac{\rho_{\text{stag}}}{2} v_{\text{stag}}^2$$

with $v_{\text{stag}} = 0$ and $\rho = \frac{p}{RT}$. Thus the stagnation pressure is

$$p_{\text{stag}} = p_2 + \frac{p_2 v_2^2}{2RT_2} = 416 \text{ kPa.}$$

The mean temperature computed from the exhaust temperature and the stagnation temperature is

$$T_m = \frac{T_2 + T_{\text{stag}}}{2} = 2404 \text{ K.}$$

Now the molar heat capacities of water vapor and carbon dioxide are $Mc_{pm\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 60.3 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$ and $Mc_{pm\text{CO}_2} = 74.9 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$. From this the molar heat capacity of the mixture can be computed as before:

$$Mc_{pm} = r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} Mc_{pm\text{H}_2\text{O}} + r_{\text{CO}_2} Mc_{pm\text{CO}_2} = 67.7 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$$

Accordingly, the isentropic exponent is

$$\kappa_m = \frac{Mc_{pm}}{Mc_{pm} - R^*} = 1.14.$$

From this the stagnation temperature can be determined as follows:

$$T_{\text{stag}} = T_2 \left(\frac{p_{\text{stag}}}{p_2} \right)^{\frac{\kappa_m - 1}{\kappa_m}} = 2614 \text{ K}$$

The nozzle exit velocity decelerates to a complete isentropic slow down at the crest of the flame deflector assuming that there is no cooling. The resulting stagnation temperature of 2614 K remains constant on the overall pipe studded surface since the velocity is reduced to zero in the boundary layer as well. This is due to the friction at the pipe surfaces.⁶ This heat has to be dissipated by water cooling under a first assumption of cooling the exhaust gas down to approximately $T_k = 400 \text{ K}$.

The mean exhaust gas temperature during the cooling process can be calculated as

$$T_{mk} = \frac{T_{\text{stag}} + T_k}{2} = 1507 \text{ K.}$$

Accordingly the molar isobaric heat capacity of the water is $Mc_{pm\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 47.5 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$ while that of the carbon dioxide is $Mc_{pm\text{CO}_2} = 58.7 \text{ kJ/kmol K}$. Thus, the isobaric molar heat capacity of the exhaust gas mixture is

$$Mc_{pmk} = r_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} Mc_{pm\text{H}_2\text{O}} + r_{\text{CO}_2} Mc_{pm\text{CO}_2} = 53.2 \text{ kJ/kmol K.}$$

⁶See (Albring, 1991, p. 111).

The isobaric heat capacity is thus

$$c_{pmk} = \frac{M c_{pmk}}{M} = 1.71 \text{ kJ/kg K.}$$

These calculations yield the thermal power

$$\dot{Q} = c_{pmk} \dot{m} (T_{\text{stag}} - T_k) = 0.49 \text{ GW,}$$

which is in good accordance with $\dot{Q} = F v_2 = F^2 / \dot{m} = 0.48 \text{ GW} = 133.3 \text{ kWh/s}$.⁷

To simplify things, the following calculation of the cooling water mass flow is based on the assumption $\dot{Q} = 0.48 \text{ GW} = 133.3 \text{ kWh/s}$. The overall energy which is transferred during a burn time of 60 s is thus $Q = 8000 \text{ kWh}$.

The computation is approximate for the following reasons: For lack of anything better, the isobaric heat capacity c_p was calculated according to the applied formula although it is valid up to approximately 1300 K only. Another source of uncertainty may derive from the fuel mixture ratio, which could not be confirmed by any other reference. The nozzle exit diameter of 710 mm was verified by own measurements at three pieces of hardware in Berlin and Peenemünde and from one drawing shown by Phieler (2019). However, during development of the A4 rocket experiments with other nozzle geometries were performed as well.

3.1. Heat transfer in the flame deflector

The crest of the 7.85 m wide flame deflector is hit by a gas flow consisting of water vapor and carbon dioxide with a supersonic velocity of 1923 m/s, generating a stagnation temperature of 2614 K, which would remain constant on the overall surface area if not being cooled down. The velocity is generated by a convergent/divergent Laval nozzle with a sonic velocity of around 920 m/s in the throat. The gas mass flow is 130 kg/s, the molar flow is 4.17 kmol/s and the volume flow at the nozzle exit is 762 m³/s. The molar mass is 31.2 kmol/kg, similar to that of air. The gas mass flow consists of 28% water vapor and 72% carbon dioxide.

How is the thermal gas heat of 0.48 GW transferred to the water cooled flame deflector during a burn time of one minute, within which the temperature has to be reduced from 2614 K to around 400 K? It is clear that an additional external cooling water spraying system is required as no steel would be able to withstand these conditions. The laws of heat transfer allow a satisfactory approximation as will be shown in the following.

Figure 5 shows an original drawing of the flame deflector while figure 6 shows a photograph of the actual structure following a catastrophically failed test run. The water cooling pipes can be clearly seen covering the overall flame deflector.

⁷Other sources, such as (A4, 1945, p. 17) or Phieler (2019) specify the thermal power as 0.515 GW and 0.5 GW respectively, which also is in good accordance with the above calculations.

Figure 5: Flame deflector (original drawing, source: Bundesarchiv Freiburg, Signatur RH8/4016K/E839A)

Figure 6: Flame deflector after a test failure (photo from 1941, Sig. B154/41 BSM, Archive Deutsches Museum) – note the destroyed rocket combustion chamber and nozzle in the lower left

Figure 7: Schematic of flame deflector (detail)

Figure 8: Detail of the steam/water collector within the flame deflector

Figure 9: Array of pipes on the flame deflector surface

Figure 7 shows a horizontal side view sketch (upper half) and the view from above (lower half) of the flame deflector structure.⁸

Figure 8 shows a schematic of the water vapor collector within the flame deflector which will be used to calculate the pressure losses in the following. The array of pipes covering the flame deflector surface is shown in detail in figure 9. A setup like this allows most of the pipe circumference (about 98%) to be in contact with the hot exhaust gases. The distance between two adjacent pipes is estimated as being $a = 2$ mm. The flame deflector has a width of 7.85 m. The outer diameter of the pipes is $d_a = 33.7$ mm. The pipes are arranged in regular intervals of $s = d_a + a = 35.7$ mm. So the number of pipes is $i = 7850 \text{ mm} / 35.7 \text{ mm} = 220$ per side.

By rolling out all pipe perimeters on a plane we get the effective heat transfer flame deflector width $B = 0.0337 \text{ m} \cdot \pi \cdot 0.98 \cdot 220 = 22.8 \text{ m}$. The overall length of the pipes for both sides of the deflector is $L = 2 \cdot 7.5 \text{ m} = 15 \text{ m}$ (primary flow pipes) plus $2 \cdot 1 \text{ m} = 2 \text{ m}$ (secondary flow pipes). The values 7.5 m and 1 m were derived from the original drawing figure 5. Thus the heat transfer area is $A = 22.8 \text{ m}(15 \text{ m} + 2 \text{ m}) = 387.6 \text{ m}^2$.

⁸DN denotes the nominal diameter of the pipes in mm.

3.2. Injected cooling water

The additional amount of injected cooling water was iteratively determined to be 90 l/s under the condition of a mixing temperature for the surface of the steel pipes not to exceed 1000°C. The exhaust gas temperature is $T_{\text{stag}} = 2614$ K and the injection water temperature is $T_a = 303$ K with a boiling temperature of $T_b = 373$ K.

It is $\dot{Q}_{\text{emitted}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{absorbed}}$ with

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{emitted}} = \dot{m}c_{\text{pm}}(T_{\text{stag}} - T_m) \text{ and} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{absorbed}} = \dot{m}_{\text{spray}}c(T_b - T_a) + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}}r_1 + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}}c_{\text{steam}}(T_m - T_b). \quad (2)$$

Here r_1 denotes the evaporation heat of the cooling spray water at atmospheric pressure, c is the specific heat capacity of liquid water, c_{steam} is the specific heat capacity of the evaporated cooling spray water, c_{pm} is the mean isobaric heat capacity between the temperatures T_{stag} and T_m . T_m represents the mixing temperature of the exhaust gas and the cooling spray water:

$$T_m = \frac{T_{\text{stag}} - \frac{C_2}{C_1} + \frac{C_3}{C_1}T_b}{1 + \frac{C_3}{C_1}} = 830^\circ \text{ C}$$

with the following auxiliary variables:

$$C_1 = \dot{m}c_{\text{pm}}$$

$$C_2 = \dot{m}_{\text{spray}}c(T_b - T_a) + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}}r_1$$

$$C_3 = \dot{m}_{\text{spray}}c_{\text{steam}}$$

Inserting this into (1) and (2) yields $\dot{Q}_{\text{emitted}} = 0.3674 \text{ GW} = \dot{Q}_{\text{absorbed}}$. Thus just the external spray water cooling already removes 0.3674 GW of heat which leaves 0.113 GW to be removed by the cooling pipes.⁹

3.3. Heat flows in flame deflector pipes

Regarding the piping we have to take two structures into account:

Primary flow: Piping on deflector surface, water flow denoted by \dot{m}_{primary}

Secondary flow: Piping on deflector crest, water flow denoted by $\dot{m}_{\text{secondary}}$

We assume $\dot{m}_{\text{primary}} = 50 \text{ kg/s}$ and $\dot{m}_{\text{secondary}} = 10 \text{ kg/s}$ with a pressure of 7 bar and a saturation temperature of 165°C and an evaporation heat of $r_7 = 2066 \text{ kJ/kg}$ at 7 bar. The indices in the following equations are with respect to the letters in figure 11. The equations correspond to the encircled

⁹When it turned out that spray cooling alone would have been sufficient, it was already too late to change the overall setup of the flame deflector. Modern test stands like that in Lampoldshausen, Germany, only use spray cooling.

Figure 10: Course of the cooling water temperature shown in the temperature-entropy diagram of water vapor

numbers in this figure, starting with 1. Lower case subscripts relate to water while upper case subscripts denote exhaust gas.

Figure 10 shows the t, s -diagram of water including the liquid phase, wet steam, and the super-heated steam. The steam content is

$$x = \frac{\text{mass of saturated steam}}{\text{mass of wet steam}} = \frac{m''}{m' + m''} \quad (3)$$

The specific volume is

$$V_{\text{sp}} = \frac{1}{\rho} = V' + x(V'' - V') \quad (4)$$

with V'' measured at the dew line $x = 1$ and V' at the boiling line $x = 0$. The dynamic viscosity is

$$\eta = (1 - x)\eta_{\text{liquid}} + x\eta_{\text{gas}}.$$

40% of the cooling water in the deflector pipes evaporate, i.e. the steam content is: $x = m''/(m' + m'') = 0.4$ So a mere 60% of the cooling water contribute to the heat flow. The saturated portion does not create any heat flow, since the temperature remains constant during evaporation.

These variables were determined iteratively leading to the mandatory equality between the heat flows determined by thermodynamics and the formulae of the heat transfer laws.

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{jk}} = \dot{m}_{\text{primary}}c(T_k - T_j) = 0.0282 \text{ GW} \quad \text{liquid water, ①}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{kl}} = \dot{m}_{\text{primary}}r_7 = 0.062 \text{ GW} \quad \text{boiling water, ②}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{lm}} = \dot{m}_{\text{primary}}c_{\text{pm}}(T_m - T_l) = 0 \text{ GW} \quad \text{saturated steam, ③}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{no}} = \dot{m}_{\text{secondary}}c(T_o - T_n) = 0.00564 \text{ GW} \quad \text{liquid water, ④}$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{op}} = \dot{m}_{\text{secondary}}r_7 = 0.0124 \text{ GW} \quad \text{boiling water, ⑤}$$

Section	ΔT_{large} [K]	ΔT_{small} [K]	ΔT_{mlog} [K]
①	554	490	521
②	643	490	563
③	643	643	643
④	756	635	694
⑤	665	635	650

Table 3: Mean logarithmic temperature difference of the various flame deflector sections

Thus the heat flow derived from thermodynamics is $\dot{Q}_{\text{thermodyn}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{jk}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{kl}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{lm}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{no}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{op}} = 0.1082 \text{ GW}$.

4. The laws of heat transfer

The water in the deflector pipes has to cool down the exhaust gas/spray water mixture from 1103 K (130 kg/s of gas and additional spray water steam of 90 kg/s). The volume fractions become 0.769 for the water steam and 0.231 for the carbon dioxide. The molar mass is 24 kg/kmol, the isobaric heat capacity is $c = 1.8 \text{ kJ/kg K}$ for section 1 and 1.88 for section 5.

On the basis of these partial water heat flows we will now derive the exhaust gas temperatures starting from the crest and ending with the deflector exit:

$$T_{\text{O}} = T_{\text{P}} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{op}}}{(\dot{m} + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}})c_{\text{pOP}}} = 800^{\circ}\text{C} \quad \textcircled{5}$$

$$T_{\text{N}} = T_{\text{O}} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{no}}}{(\dot{m} + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}})c_{\text{pNO}}} = 786^{\circ}\text{C} \quad \textcircled{4}$$

$$T_{\text{L}} = T_{\text{M}} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{lm}}}{(\dot{m} + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}})c_{\text{pLM}}} = 808^{\circ}\text{C} \quad \textcircled{3}$$

$$T_{\text{K}} = T_{\text{L}} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{kl}}}{(\dot{m} + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}})c_{\text{pKL}}} = 655^{\circ}\text{C} \quad \textcircled{2}$$

$$T_{\text{J}} = T_{\text{K}} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{jk}}}{(\dot{m} + \dot{m}_{\text{spray}})c_{\text{pJK}}} = 584^{\circ}\text{C} \quad \textcircled{1}$$

$T_{\text{M}} = 1081 \text{ K} = 808^{\circ}\text{C}$ is the mixing temperature of the gas resulting from gas already cooled down to 1059 K being mixed with hot exhaust gas of 1103 K. So the exhaust gas is cooled down in the flame deflector from 830°C to 584°C if the geometry of the deflector allows this heat transfer.

Table 3 shows the mean logarithmic temperature differences for each section of the flame deflector accounting for spray water with

$$T_{\text{mlog}} = \frac{\Delta T_{\text{large}} - \Delta T_{\text{small}}}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_{\text{large}}}{\Delta T_{\text{small}}}\right)}.$$

Figure 11: Flame deflector: Course of calculated gas and water temperatures

Regime	α [W/m ² K]	Source
Gas	528	http://schweizer-fn.de
Saturated steam	11700	http://dingler.culture.hu-berlin.de
Water in pipes	≈ 4300	http://schweizer-fn.de
Hot steam	47	http://dingler.culture.hu-berlin.de

Table 4: Heat transfer coefficients

The calculation of the heat transfer potential of the flame deflector is based on

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{actual}} = 10^{-9} k A \Delta T_{\text{mlog}}$$

The factor 10^{-9} accounts for the units m² and K to arrive at GW.

The thermal conductivity of alloyed steel is $\lambda = 21$ W/mK, and the pipe wall thickness is $\delta = 2.6$ mm, with the heat transfer coefficient α . Table 4 shows the values of this coefficient for various regimes.

The reciprocal value of the overall heat transfer coefficient k is

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{\alpha_1} + \frac{\delta}{\lambda} + \frac{1}{\alpha_2}$$

For sections ① and ④ $k = 444$ W/m²K, for sections ② and ⑤ $k = 475$ W/m²K, and for section ③ $k = 43$ W/m²K.

Table 5 shows the comparison of the heat flow according to thermodynamics and the heat flow according to the laws of heat transfer. It can be seen that the flame deflector transfers a heat energy of 0.103 GW. Together with the heat transfer by the spray water of 0.3674 GW (see section 3.2) this amounts to 0.47 GW, which is 2% less than required. Thus, the exhaust gas of the flame deflector has a slightly higher temperature than 584°C. Only 40% of the cooling water evaporate in the pipes, 60% exit as liquid water at 7 bar and 165°C into the collector and then into the ambient.

Section	$\dot{Q}_{\text{thermodyn}}$ [GW]	ΔT_{mlog} [K]	k [W/m ² K]	A [m ²]	$\dot{Q}_{\text{transfer}}$ [GW]
①	0.0282	521	441	27	0.00624
②	0.062	563	475	294	0.0786
③	0	643	43	8	0
④	0.00564	694	441	11	0.00339
⑤	0.0124	650	475	48	0.0148
Sum	0.1082			377	0.103

Table 5: The heat transfer potential of the flame deflector with a cooling water flow of 50 l/s in the primary flow and 10 l/s in the secondary flow

The overall cooling water flow is

$$\dot{m}_{\text{wtotal}} = \dot{m}_{\text{spray}} + \dot{m}_{\text{primary}} + \dot{m}_{\text{secondary}} = 150 \text{ l/s}$$

with $\dot{m}_{\text{spray}} = 90 \text{ l/s}$. It can be seen that cooling by spray water is much more efficient than cooling by heat transfer through pipe walls (0.3674 GW vs. 0.103 GW). Figure 12 shows the heat transfer across the cooling water pipes from exhaust gas to cooling water. The temperature gradient is steepest at the walls due to the temperature boundary layer.

The variables used in this figure are $T_G = 1103 \text{ k}$ (gas temperature), T'_G (wall temperature on the gas side), $T_W = 438 \text{ K}$ (saturated steam) resp. $T_W = 523 \text{ K}$ (hot steam), T'_W (wall temperature water side), δ (pipe wall thickness), δ_o and δ_i (outside and inside temperature boundary layer), α_W and α_G (heat transfer coefficient water side and gas side), A_G and A_m (outside pipe surface and mean pipe surface), λ (heat conductivity of steel).

The heat flow through all three layers is equal:

$$\dot{Q} = \alpha_G A_G (T_G - T'_G) = \frac{\lambda}{\delta} A_m (T'_G - T'_W) = \alpha_W A_q (T'_G - T_W)$$

This yields $T'_G \approx T'_W$ and $A_G \approx A_W$. (For thin pipes the outer and inner surface are approximately equal.) Thus we get

$$\alpha_G (T_G - T'_G) = \alpha_W (T'_G - T_W) \text{ and}$$

$$T'_G = T'_W = \frac{T_G + \frac{\alpha_W}{\alpha_G} T_W}{1 + \frac{\alpha_W}{\alpha_G}}$$

For saturated steam we have $\alpha_W = 4300 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and $\alpha_G = 528 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ yielding $T'_G = 510 \text{ K} = 238^\circ\text{C}$. For hot steam have $\alpha_W = 47 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and $\alpha_G = 528 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ yielding $T'_G = 1048 \text{ K} = 776^\circ$.

These results show that due to the temperature boundary layer the surface temperature of the deflector pipes is 510 K. In the upper part of the deflector the surface temperature may reach 1048 K because it cannot be excluded that parts of the pipes are partially filled with superheated steam. The results also

show that the temperature limit for steel is not reached. So the split-up of the cooling water flows of 90 l/s spray water and 60 l/s pipe water can well be changed to e.g. 80 vs. 70 l/s which would increase the pipe pressure loss and hence the pump power consumption.

5. Calculation of pressure losses

Pressure loss in the flame deflector pipes due to the pipe length and obstructions within the pipes (including bends, valves etc.):

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta p &= \lambda \frac{l}{d} \rho \frac{v^2}{2} 10^{-5} \text{ [bar]} && \text{due to pipe length} \\ \Delta p &= \zeta \rho \frac{v^2}{2} 10^{-5} \text{ [bar]} && \text{due to obstructions}\end{aligned}$$

Here, λ denotes the pipe friction coefficient, l is the length, d the diameter, ρ the density of the water and water vapor and v the velocity.

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} 0.32/\sqrt[4]{Re} & \text{for } 2300 < Re < 10^5 \\ 0.0032 + 0.221/Re^{0.237} & \text{for } 10^5 < Re < 10^8 \end{cases}$$

Thus the mean value of λ is 0.02. Re denotes the Reynolds number:

$$Re = \frac{vd\rho}{\eta} 10^6,$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity. Density ρ and steam content x are defined in equations (4) and (3). The velocity is

$$\begin{aligned}v &= \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{primary}}}{A\rho} \text{ or} \\ v &= \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{primary}} + \dot{m}_{\text{secondary}}}{A\rho} \text{ and} \\ v &= \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{primary}}}{2iA\rho} \text{ (within the pipes)}\end{aligned}$$

with $\dot{m}_{\text{primary}} = 50$ kg/s and $\dot{m}_{\text{1pipe}} = 0.1136$ kg/s. The inner pipe diameter is $d_i = 0.0285$ m yielding the throughflow area $A = 6.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m² of a pipe.

Table 6 shows the calculation of pressure losses and fluid power for the 15 different elements. The return line must have a valve (probably a gate valve) in order to reduce the system pressure of 7 bar to ambient conditions of the reservoirs. This valve makes up the lion's share of the pressure losses and fluid powers. The pressure losses of these 15 elements are added up. The fluid power of each element is mass flow times pressure loss divided by density. The superposition eventually yields the power the pumps have to provide to overcome the pressure losses. It has to be kept in mind that the water pressure in the manifold of 7 bar (necessary to overcome the system resistance which is

Element	State	T [K]	ρ [kgm ⁻³]	A [m ²]	v [m/s]	d [m]	l [m]	λ/d	ζ	Δp [bar]	p [bar]	\dot{m} [kg/s]	P [kW]
intake headers	water	303	1000	0.5	0.0497	0.8	90	2.25		≈ 0	7	50	≈ 0
bends upstream of headers	water	303	1000	0.5	0.0497	0.8			0.3	≈ 0	7	50	≈ 0
2 headers	water	303	1000	0.5	0.0497	0.8			1.28	≈ 0	7	50	≈ 0
440 pipe bends header \rightarrow deflector	water	303	1000	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.18	0.0285	2.5	1.8		≈ 0	7	50	≈ 0
440 deflector pipes	water $x = 0$	438	902	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.197	0.0285	0	0		≈ 0	7	50	≈ 0
	wet steam $x = 0.05$	438	68.1	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	2.61	0.0285	0.5	0.35		≈ 0	7	50	≈ 0
	wet steam $x = 0.1$	438	35.4	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	5.02	0.0285	1.0	0.7		0.003	≈ 7	50	4.2
	wet steam $x = 0.2$	438	18.0	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	9.87	0.0285	1.5	1.0		0.009	7.01	50	2.5
	wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	19.5	0.0285	2.0	1.4		0.024	7.04	50	13.3
wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	19.5	0.0285	2.0	1.4		0.024	7.04	50	13.2	
180° bends end of deflector pipes	wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-4}$	19.5	0.0285			1.62	0.028	7.09	50	15.4
collector in deflector	wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1	0.78	8.4				1.31	0.004	7.09	60	2.6
exit deflector with bend	wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1	0.78	8.4	1.0			1.7	0.005	7.1	60	3.3
return line to reservoirs +2 bends	wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1	0.5	13.2	0.8	90	2.25	2 · 0.3	0.018 0.005	7.12	60	15.2
gate valve upstream reservoir	wet steam $x = 0.4$	438	9.1			0.8			> 700	6.12	7.12 \rightarrow 1.0	60	4035
$\Sigma P =$												4105	

Table 6: Calculation of pressure losses and fluid powers for the primary flow

required to give the right steam conditions in the heat exchanger) leads to an evaporating temperature of as high as 165°C. The mandatory equality of the heat flow by thermodynamics and the heat flow by heat transfer laws provides evidence that not all of the cooling water in the pipes evaporated, so this must be accounted for in the calculations.¹⁰

It is unknown where the spray water came from. No branch-off from the main pipes can be detected in the original drawings. However, these show 20 break-throughs labelled “Minimax“, 30 × 15 cm in the concrete side walls of the deflector structure. They are located at 1.5 m distance corresponding exactly to the curvature of the pipes. “Minimax” is well known in Germany for fire extinguishing equipment, so it may well be that 20 “Minimax” cartridges, each filled with 270 kg of pressurized water, might have been used to accomplish the water injection, providing 4.5 l/s each for the test time of 60 s, thus providing the necessary 90 l/s. That seems not to be too far fetched.

The calculation of pressure losses and power requirements for the secondary flow at the crest of the flame deflector was conducted analogously to the primary flow, beginning with the intake flow pipe, through the bend, a conical diffuser, the header, the bends at the crest, and finally to the nozzles in the collector, where the secondary flow joins the primary flow. The results show that the pressure loss and associated power in the secondary pipe system are negligible, although the secondary pump has to maintain the 7 bar level in the collector of the deflector, delivering 10 l/s of water and saturated steam into the primary flow.

Figure 13 shows the overall piping system. Two pumps provide the cooling water for the primary flow while one pump feeds the secondary flow. Within

¹⁰A reduction of pressure is basically possible but yields unrealistically high velocities in the pipes of the flame deflector.

Figure 12: Heat transfer across the cooling water pipes from exhaust gas to cooling water showing the course of temperature

Figure 13: Schematic of the cooling water cycle in the flame deflector, plausibly derived from the original drawing (figure 5). Intake header crest: secondary flow.

the deflector body steam and residual water of all three pumps are collected and directed towards the reservoirs. The evaporated water has to be supplemented before the next test run.

Figure 14 shows the performance curve of one pump and the system resistance of the flame deflector (primary flow). The intersection of pump performance and system resistance curve is the actual operating point. In case there is a higher system resistance than calculated, the operating point moves to a smaller mass flow, point “a”, thus jeopardizing the cooling of the exhaust gas. Therefore the pump must have a sufficient reserve to attain the specified mass flow, point “b”.

The corresponding fluid powers of the pumps are

$$P_{\text{primary}} = \frac{P}{\eta} = 5864 \text{ kW}$$

Figure 14: Pump performance curve and system resistance of flame deflector, primary flow (not to scale)

	Primary flow	Secondary flow
Fluid power of one pump	2930 kW	9.4 kW
+25% excess for uncertainties	3660 kW	11.8 kW
Mechanical losses (bearings, seals)	50 kW	1 kW
System derating (particles deposits, roughness)	20 kW	1 kW
Power at motor coupling	3730 kW	13.8 kW
Motor name plate rating (+ $\approx 10\%$)	4100 kW	15 kW

Table 7: Motor rating scenarios

$$P_{\text{secondary}} = \dot{m}_{\text{secondary}} \frac{\Delta p}{\rho \eta} = 9.4 \text{ kW}$$

with η denoting the pump efficiency, assumed to be 0.7 for the primary pumps and 0.65 for the secondary pump.

The 5864 kW are by two pumps of ≈ 2930 kW each, while the single pump for the secondary flow only has to deliver 9.4 kW. To determine the required motor rating the scenarios shown in table 7 are used. The pumps were of the centrifugal type, preferably with no gear box between pump and motor, water at atmospheric suction.¹¹

6. Summary

The results of the attempted reverse aero-thermodynamic design computation of the Aggregate 4 during its full-load ground test shows that the testing could have probably been conducted in the way described in this paper. The calculations give an impression about the determining criteria and how the heat transfer could have been accomplished, what pressures and temperatures were

¹¹It is unknown how the flow was controlled. It is possible that the valve was only cracked open to get the flow started and the opened fully when the rocket engine was fired up.

involved, which cooling water amounts were necessary to transfer the enormous heat of 480 MW from the rocket exhaust nozzle to the hot flame deflector and how high the power output of the water pumps had to be to pump the cooling water through the branched manifold of the deflector structure.

The reverse engineering approach presented in this paper must necessarily be more ambiguous than the normal straightforward engineering method. Forward engineering philosophy follows a theory with a mathematical model resulting in a well defined geometric structure with only marginal variation options. Reverse engineering on the other hand is per se ambiguous and may result in multiple solutions. So the calculation proposed is only one possibility the scientists and engineers of the early 1940s may have had to face the challenge of transferring the enormous heat on the test stand.

Philosophical point: The disciplines aero-thermodynamics, heat transfer and hydraulics applied in this reverse engineering approach were part of the curriculum of the engineers of the 1930s and 1940s. The technical knowledge of our time has only gradually improved by having more empirical data at our disposal like material characteristics and pipe friction coefficients. Of course, the fundamental laws of physics have not been changed during the last 80 years. A certain appreciable difference between now and then is an improved understanding of the effects of the boundary layer theory of fluid dynamics. Today we understand that the velocity of a fluid passing a surface is zero at the surface itself, due to wall friction. Consequently, the total kinetic energy is converted into heat which results in a corresponding increase in temperature. So, the surfaces of the cooling pipes are exposed to the same very high temperature as the stagnation point. This is one of today's benefits of hindsight.

Maybe one day a comparison will be possible when the original computations of the 1940s might be found and retrieved from one of the archives.

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